

Ion-Solvent Interactions : Conductance Studies of Tetraalkylammonium Ions in Ethanol + Water Mixtures

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In order to understand the nature of ion-solvent interactions and structural changes of the solvent mixtures associated with the addition of ions, conductance measurements of the tetraalkylammonium halides in ethanol + water mixtures were made. The results have been analysed using the Fuoss equations. In absence of transference number values, the single ion values of tetraalkylammonium ions at 16.4, 34.4, 54.1 and 76 wt% of ethanol have been calculated using reference electrolyte method taking Bu₄NBPh₄ as the electrolyte. The variation of Λ^0 and $\Lambda^0\eta_0$ or $\Lambda^{0\pm}\eta_0$ with solvent composition has been interpreted in terms of structural changes associated with the addition of electrolytes. Most of the electrolytes can be regarded to be associated in the solvent mixtures.

The importance of the studies of ion-solvent interactions has been widely stressed. Valuable informations on ion-solvent interactions and solvational behaviour of electrolytes can be obtained from studies of transport properties like viscosity and conductance measurements. The tetraalkylammonium salts have attracted considerable attention due to the amphiphilic nature of these electrolytes¹. Conductance studies of tetraalkylammonium halides in water have been made by Evans and Kay². The studies have been extended to aqueous, non-aqueous and mixed solvents²⁻⁷. Ion conductances of tetraalkylammonium salts (upto tetra-butyl-ammonium ion) in ethanol+water, dioxane+water and t-butanol+water have been studied extensively by Kay *et al.*^{3,4} to understand the solvent structures of aquo-organic mixtures. Kay and Broadwater⁴ used Fuoss-Onsager conductance equation. They also determined transference numbers by the moving boundary method and obtained the single ion conductance values of ions. However, some of these compounds have not been studied or not studied throughout the composition range. As part of our programme to study ion-solvent interactions of electrolytes in different mixed solvents, conductance studies on some tetraalkylammonium halides in ethanol+water mixtures have been undertaken. We used Shedlovsky's equation⁸ to have preliminary ideas of 'association constants'. However, in order to get better results the Fuoss equation⁹ was then used. The single ion conductance values of the tetraalkylammonium ions at 16.4, 34.4, 54.1 and 76.0 wt% of ethanol were determined using the reference electrolyte (Bu₄NBPh₄) method. The variation of the Walden product with solvent composition was studied to have some idea regarding the effect of tetraalkylammonium ions on the structure of the solvent mixtures. The results are presented in this communication.

Results and Discussion

The conductance data were analysed using Shedlovsky's method involving the sets of equation^{8,10-13},

$$\frac{1}{S\Lambda} = \frac{1}{\Lambda_0} + \frac{C\Lambda S f^{\frac{1}{2}} K_A}{\Lambda_0^2} \quad (1)$$

where $S = 1/F(x)$ is a known function of $x [(A + BA_0) \sqrt{CA} / \Lambda_0^{3/2}]$, A and B are Onsager constants. The initial values of Λ_0 have been obtained from the plot of Λ against $C^{1/2}$. The association constants (K_A) and the limiting equivalent conductance (Λ_0) have been iteratively calculated by a least-square treatment using a basic programme (Wipre Z650). The mean activity coefficient of ions has been calculated in the way suggested by Justice¹². The Λ_0 and K_A values thus obtained are given in Table 1. Since the K_A values for most of these compounds have been found to be considerably greater than 10, they are regarded to be highly associated in aqueous and aquo-organic solvents. The accurate results for Λ_0 for these compounds can be obtained using Fuoss-Onsager equation and we have adopted the method of computation proposed by Fuoss⁹. The data were analysed using the following set of equations,

$$\Lambda = \rho[\Lambda_0(1 + RX) + EL] \quad (2)$$

$$\rho = (1 - \alpha(1 - \gamma)) \quad (3)$$

$$\gamma = 1 - K_A C \gamma^2 f^2 \quad (4)$$

$$-f \ln \gamma = \beta \frac{K}{2} (1 + k.R) \quad (5)$$

$$\beta = \frac{e^2}{\epsilon ET} \quad (6)$$

$$K_A = K_R/(1 - \alpha) = K_R (1 + K_S) \quad (7)$$

RX and EL are relaxation and hydrodynamic terms, respectively. Expressions for RX and EL terms and other terms have the same significance as given by Fuoss⁹. The computation was done using the program of Fuoss. The problem was solved by finding the values of Λ_0 and α which minimised

$$\sigma^2 = \sum_j \frac{(\Lambda_j(\text{cal}) - \Lambda_j(\text{obs}))^2}{n-2} \quad (8)$$

for a sequence of R values and the plotting $\sigma\% = 100\sigma/\Lambda_0$ against R . The best-fit value R corresponds to minimum in the $\sigma\%-R$ curve. First a coarse scan for all salts was done from $R=2$ to $R=15$ with increment of the unit value. But since no maximum was observed and the computations were done fixing $R=\beta/2$. The K_A , Λ_0 and $\sigma\%$ are given in Table 2.

The limiting conductance (Λ_0) and association constant (K_A) values obtained by using Shedlovsky's equation and the corresponding values of the constants using Fuoss equation are given in Tables 1 and 2; the values are close. However, in view of inadequacy of our measurements, the accuracy of the results can be regarded to be within 0.5%.

The Λ_0 values in water have been found to be in agreement with the reported values³ though slight differences, probably due to the use of Fuoss (1978) equation exist. Naturally this will be reflected in the single ion values also. The Λ_0 values have been found to decrease with increasing percentages of organic solvents and pass through minima at about 54–64 wt% of alcohol. In order to have a better insight regarding ion-solvent interactions, it is desirable to have the single ion values. Accurate transference number in these aquo-binary mixtures are needed to derive single ion values. However, these data are lacking in most cases. Therefore, we used the 'reference electrolyte' method for the division of Λ^0 to get single ion values¹⁴. Bu_4NBPh_4 has been used as the 'reference electrolyte'. The Λ_0 (Bu_4NBPh_4) values have been obtained from the relation,

$$\Lambda^0(\text{Bu}_4\text{NBPh}_4) = \Lambda^0(\text{Bu}_7\text{NCl}) + \Lambda^0(\text{NaBPh}_4) - \Lambda^0(\text{NaCl}) \quad (9)$$

Bu_4NBPh_4 , first utilised by Fuoss and Hirst¹⁴, is adjudged to be one of the best 'reference electrolyte' to calculate the limiting ion conductances in organic solvents^{14,15}.

However, instead of taking $\lambda + \text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+ = \lambda - \text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-$,
The $\frac{\lambda^{\circ}\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}{\lambda^{\circ}\text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-} \left(= \frac{\gamma(\text{Ph}_4\text{B}^-)}{\gamma(\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+)} = \frac{5.33}{5.00} \right) = 1.07$

TABLE 1—EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES AND ASSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF TETRAALKYL COMPOUNDS IN EtOH+H₂O MIXTURE AT 298 K USING SHEDLOVSKY'S METHOD

EtOH wt %	Pr ₄ NBr		Pe ₄ NBr		Bu ₄ NI		Pr ₄ NI		Bu ₄ NCl	
	Λ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	K_A	Λ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	K_A	Λ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	K_A	Λ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	K_A	Λ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	K_A
0.0	97.27	5.94	94.61	27.54	94.78	24.57	99.54	6.68	94.18	16.31
8.0	76.72	13.35	69.59	22.60	62.10	3.05	77.59	10.79	71.09	17.95
16.4	58.32	6.38	56.20	24.63	56.25	20.40	58.41	12.94	55.38	13.50
25.3	49.09	10.80	46.38	27.47	46.22	21.63	47.19	6.89	43.88	15.58
34.4	41.50	4.25	37.28	11.83	38.60	15.32	41.22	5.65	37.84	11.81
44.0	38.74	6.02	36.94	27.44	37.06	20.79	38.60	9.12	34.81	10.45
54.1	37.98	20.99	34.22	16.16	35.90	7.20	37.47	6.86	32.89	7.47
64.7	38.08	27.77	34.02	20.61	35.72	9.70	36.05	4.83	32.65	7.17
76.0	39.14	40.07	34.27	21.09	36.66	10.01	37.99	3.79	—	—
87.6	41.96	59.63	36.40	45.16	38.01	23.81	41.38	23.03	—	—
100	44.66	103.65	40.10	105.25	42.29	70.88	46.49	96.77	—	—

TABLE 2—LIMITING EQUIVALENT CONDUCTANCES OF TETRAALKYLAMMONIUM COMPOUNDS USING FUOSS (1978) EQUATION AT 298 K

EtOH wt %	$R=\beta/2$	Pr ₄ NBr			Pe ₄ NBr			Bu ₄ NI			Pr ₄ NI			Bu ₄ NCl		
		Λ_0 $\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2$	K_A	σ %												
0.0	3.56	99.88	6.843	0.715	95.179	31.00	1.082	96.10	35.01	1.464	99.459	7.084	2.270	95.30	16.787	0.274
8.0	3.785	76.96	15.102	1.866	69.85	24.922	0.764	62.10	3.050	1.502	77.604	11.189	2.344	71.12	18.659	0.343
16.4	3.98	58.41	7.631	0.942	56.55	28.325	1.349	56.31	21.561	0.241	58.531	12.911	1.948	55.43	14.595	0.538
23.3	4.29	49.41	14.19	2.576	46.68	31.526	1.323	46.41	24.449	0.729	47.19	7.579	2.360	43.95	17.184	0.320
34.4	4.795	41.59	6.487	0.971	37.34	13.961	0.176	38.76	18.627	0.997	41.30	7.447	3.271	37.90	13.856	1.148
44.0	5.325	38.83	8.938	0.506	37.32	35.01	1.464	37.13	23.762	0.381	38.63	11.097	2.401	34.88	13.428	0.572
54.1	5.999	38.23	17.302	1.096	34.22	21.659	1.013	35.97	10.746	2.477	37.67	11.482	4.057	32.96	11.578	0.561
64.7	6.84	38.39	37.308	0.625	34.15	27.754	0.575	35.72	9.301	2.495	36.05	4.730	4.856	32.79	14.177	0.283
76.0	8.045	39.14	56.617	0.5999	34.26	34.168	0.380	36.87	20.654	4.488	38.38	5.972	5.608	—	—	—
87.6	9.445	41.81	68.213	1.050	36.11	50.871	1.005	38.01	23.805	3.892	40.63	19.256	3.64	—	—	—
100.0	11.075	42.36	74.868	3.376	39.15	96.574	1.851	42.29	70.875	2.852	44.96	76.435	2.44	—	—	—

has been utilised for division.

The value was obtained based on the radii of ions determined by Gill^{16,17} or Krumgalz¹⁸. A critical evaluation of the method has already been made^{19,20}. The Λ° values of NaCl, Bu₄NCl and NaBPh₄ were taken from our previous works. Our value $\Lambda^\circ_{\text{NaCl}}$ (126.56 Ω^{-1} cm²) in water is in agreement with the literature value (126.45 Ω^{-1} cm²)²². The λ° values of other ions in water at 298 K have been calculated using λ° values of Na⁺ Cl⁻ ions (Table 3). The calculated values of $\lambda^\circ_{\text{BPh}_4^-}$ and $\lambda^\circ_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}$ (at 298 K) in water are found to be 18.58 and 19.75 Ω^{-1} cm² respectively, and $\lambda^\circ_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}/\lambda^\circ_{\text{BPh}_4^-}$ to be 1.063²¹ or ($\lambda^\circ_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+}/\lambda^\circ_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+\text{BPh}_4^-}$ = 0.515).

TABLE 3—LIMITING ION CONDUCTANCE VALUES (λ°) OF TETRAALKYL COMPOUNDS IN EtOH + H₂O MIXTURES AT 298 K

EtOH wt %	Bu ₄ N	Pr ₄ N ⁺	Pe ₄ N ⁺	Na ⁺	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	I ⁻
0.0	19.30	23.20	17.76	50.70	76.40	78.20	77.00
	(19.10) ^a	(22.46) ^a			(76.20) ^a	(77.42) ^a	(77.00) ^a
16.4	12.29	14.51	12.65	36.20	52.86	43.90	44.02
34.4	5.53	8.07	3.82	30.04	45.29	33.52	33.23
54.1	11.25	12.95	8.94	20.65	34.05	25.28	24.72
76.0	13.28	14.79	9.92	20.02	26.52	24.35	23.59
100.0	19.20	23.10	16.29	20.30	21.90	23.80	27.00

^aExperimental value.

The constancy of the λ ratio in aqueous mixed and non-aqueous solvents^{14,15} suggests that these large tetraalkyl or tetraarylammonium ions are almost proportionally hydrated due to hydrophobic interactions and similarly desolvated in non-aqueous solvents.

From the single ion conductance values in mixed solvents (Table 3), it is found that the values for tetraalkylammonium ions decrease with increase in ethanol content to reach minimum at ~34 wt% of ethanol, beyond which the conductance values increase. However, the single ion conductance values of Cl⁻ and Br⁻ ions decrease continuously whereas a minimum is observed at 76 wt% for the I⁻ ion. The λ°_+ of tetraalkylammonium ions changes in the order: $\lambda^\circ_{\text{Pr}_4\text{N}^+} > \lambda^\circ_{\text{Bu}_4\text{N}^+} > \lambda^\circ_{\text{Pe}_4\text{N}^+}$, i.e. in order of the increasing size of the tetraalkylammonium ions.

The nature of ion-solvent interactions may probably be better understood from the variation of Walden product of ions with solvent composition (Table 4). The variation of the limiting equivalent conductance of the salts with solvent composition is shown in Table 2. The results show that the conductance decreases with the increase in viscosity of the solvent mixtures and the maximum in viscosity in the solvent mixtures almost coincides with the observed minimum in Λ° . The results show that the hydrodynamic viscous force is of importance in all the cases but the difference in solvation of the ions (in mixed solvents)

TABLE 4—WALDEN PRODUCT FOR THE SINGLE ION VALUES OF TETRAALKYL COMPOUNDS IN EtOH + H₂O MIXTURE AT 298 K ($\lambda^\circ_+\eta_0$) AND ($\lambda^\circ_-\eta_0$)

EtOH wt %	Bu ₄ N ⁺	Pr ₄ N ⁺	Pe ₄ N ⁺	Na ⁺	Cl ⁻	Br ⁻	I ⁻
0.0	0.172	0.207	0.158	0.447	0.680	0.696	0.686
16.4	0.203	0.239	0.209	0.614	0.869	0.724	0.726
34.4	0.124	0.181	0.086	0.665	1.016	0.752	0.746
54.1	0.259	0.298	0.206	0.470	0.783	0.581	0.569
76.0	0.243	0.271	0.182	0.36 ^o	0.485	0.446	0.432
100	0.215	0.252	0.177	0.221	0.238	0.259	0.294

due to changed ion-solvent interactions is responsible for the change in mobility of the ions and hence Λ° values of electrolytes.

The assumption that the dielectric constant of the medium is not involved²³ in affecting the λ° values since the ionisation would be complete at infinite dilution, appears to be untenable, as the change in the λ° values is obviously not due to the change in the number of ions. The difference in the mobility of the ions and the resistance to the movement of ions through the solvent media are responsible for change in λ°_\pm of ions.

Among other factors the equivalent conductance of an ion at infinite dilution is likely to depend on: (i) solvation of ions, (ii) the rate of flow of ions through the holes under the influence of electric field which is likely to be determined by the energy required to occupy the hole into which the ion jumps plus that required to break the bonds with other molecules and (iii) the dielectric constant of the solvent.

The cations are strongly bonded with water molecules and in the present case, the extent of this depends on the nature of the tetraalkylammonium ions and the hydrophobic group present in it. Though the hydrodynamic entity in the case of the cations is likely to be larger in water than that in alcohol+water mixtures but the increased value of λ° in water may be due to the greater freedom of ions to move through the polar hydrogen bonded solvent system having high dielectric constant.

A satisfactory expression for the variation of Walden product with solvent composition is lacking though several attempts have been made²³⁻²⁶. It is well-known that ion-solvent interactions are very specific in nature depending upon the ion and the solvent.

The variation of Walden product and the existence of maxima or minima of tetraalkylammonium ions have been interpreted by Kay *et al.*^{3,4} and Singh *et al.*²⁷ using solvent-sorting model where the large tetraalkylammonium ions are supposed not to carry definite number of solvent molecules in the primary solvation shell but create in their surroundings a sheath of tightly packed water molecules which lowers the mobility. However, this view appears to be incompatible with the fact that these molecules have high solvation numbers and form solid state clathrate hydrates²⁸. However, attempts

have been made to correlate the variation of Walden products with solvent composition in terms of limiting molar volumes V_{ϕ}^{0+} of ions which are related to conductance of ions and hence, the structural changes of the solvent-mixture.

Thus, $V_{\phi}^{0+} = V_i^+ + V_e^+ + V_s^{+29,30}$, where V_i^+ representing the intrinsic volume of the ion, is positive and increases with the size of the ion and is independent of the solvent composition; V_e^+ is a negative term and represents the electrostriction of the solvent whose value decreases with the increasing size of the ion, but its contribution appears to be small with the change in solvent composition; V_s^+ representing structural contribution, consists of two opposing terms, a negative cavity term arising from the placement of the ion in the cavity and a positive structural contribution arising from the reinforcement of the solvent structure around the ion. In case of tetraalkylammonium ions in water, solvodynamic entity is quite large. Addition of ethanol further enhances the 3D-structure of water around the ion which becomes maximum in the region 25–34 wt% of ethanol resulting in the decrease in λ_{ϕ}^0 values. Depolymerisation of water structure and ultimate desolvation of ions takes place with further addition of ethanol leading to decrease in viscosity and increase in λ_{ϕ}^0 beyond the region of maximum structure formation.

The variation of the Walden product in solvent mixtures obviously implies a change in the solvation pattern and a change in effective radii of the ions. The r -value of Bu_4N^+ obtained by us or by from literature³¹ (4.66 or 4.77 Å) in water is considerably lower than the value (5.0 Å) determined by Gill^{16,17} from conductometric measurements in non-aqueous aprotic solvents whereas the value determined by Krumgalz¹⁸ is 3.85 Å. Thus considerable inconsistency is apparent and in view of the lack of knowledge regarding the values of the radii of cations (of the tetraalkyl molecules), we do not consider the calculation of effective radii to be of importance.

Most of the electrolytes can be regarded to be associated as the association constants (K_A) are usually ≥ 10 but the systematic variation of the association constants has not been noted. Very little information can be given regarding the association of the electrolytes though the reduction of the dielectric constant of the medium should increase the association of ions. However, systematic investigations in different solvents are necessary to have better idea regarding ion-solvent interactions of these molecules.

Experimental

The solutions were made using triple-distilled conductivity water. Absolute alcohol (B.C.P.L., India) was treated with requisite amount of preheated calcium oxide, kept overnight, distilled, and

then refluxed with metallic sodium and distilled before use. Sodium chloride (G. R., E. Merck), tetrabutylammonium chloride, tetrapropylammonium bromide, tetrabutylammonium iodide, tetrapropylammonium iodide (all Fluka) and tetrapentylammonium bromide (Eastman) were used without purification. These were dried and kept in a vacuum desiccator. Conductance measurement was made with a Leeds Northrup 4959 conductance bridge (sensitivity of $\pm 0.1\%$). A 50 cycle signal was employed. A fairly long vertical dip-type Philips conductance cell (with glass-platinum seals) was fitted into a double-walled corning vessel containing the experimental solution. The cell constant was determined to be 0.840 cm^{-1} . The measurements were made in a thermostatic bath maintained at $298.15 \pm 0.01 \text{ K}$.

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